

IMPLICATIONS OF META-ANALYSIS FOR EDUCATIONAL RESEARCHES**Baby May D. Requitud**

Teacher III, Calangay Elementary School, Philippines

Crystal D. Requitud

Teacher III, Coralan Elementary School, Philippines

Rundel A. Moya

Special Science Teacher I, Sto. Cristo National High School, Philippines

Alicia S. Pagalanan

Head Teacher II, Calangay Elementary School, Philippines

ABSTRACT

Meta-analysis is a set of techniques used to combine the results of number of different studies to formulate a single, more precise estimate of an effect. This study assessed the level of understanding of public elementary school teachers in line with the utilization and implications of meta-analysis as statistical technique combining different findings to establish patterns, effects and trends. The study employed a sequential explanatory mixed method. Respondents of the study were the 200 public elementary school teachers in the Philippines who were randomly selected. Findings of the study revealed that teachers possessed low level of understanding on the significant implications of meta-analysis in the conduct of educational researches in terms of evidenced-based practice, identification of research gaps and theory development. Also, the study concluded that teachers obtained moderate level of understanding in defining, using and organizing meta-analysis studies in terms of applicability and variability concepts respectively. On the other hand, the teacher-respondents encountered challenges in using meta-analysis because it required advanced statistical knowledge and skills. Apparently, teacher-respondents expressed that advanced statistical knowledge hampered their comprehensive understanding in the use of meta-analysis in conducting educational researches. Thus, the study a proposed a program intervention which may help teachers improve their understanding on the use of meta-analysis in educational researches.

Keywords:

Meta-analysis, implications, educational researches, level of understanding, evidence-based, research gaps, theory development, challenges

INTRODUCTION

Educational researches are one of the critical scholarly works in the field of education, social sciences, psychology, educational management and supervision. Teachers and school heads are expected to formulate highly impactful researches that could help them addressing the pressing challenges and problems they encountered in the teaching and learning process. The primary aim of educational researches is to contribute to the development of body of knowledge in educational settings which commonly focused on the development of instruction, formulation of effective instructional materials, provision of sound and efficient school leadership and management and creation of policies and educational models. In this line, educational researches are confined within the education practitioners including school heads, teachers, learners, parents and other stakeholders. In a naked interpretation, educational researches are drawn to scientifically describe, examine and determine the significant fibers that affect the total delivery of instruction in academic communities. Following this premise, educational researches are not developed by merely observing nor collecting surface data from the members of the academic community but they are made through rigorous process that entails structured and highly systematized procedures. Use of highly systematic procedures and processes are inherent nature of a

research. In this regard, educational researches are significantly concentrated on the development of education. In fact, in the Philippine educational context, educational researches are administered in order to create scientific solutions to the problems and challenges encountered by school heads, teachers and learners as primary components of Philippine education system aside from the examination of curriculum, leadership and managerial practices and the like. Along this line, common educational researches administered by practitioners, graduate students and independent researchers fall within the principles of quantitative and qualitative research designs. Highly complex and intricate structures of educational researches are less emphasized. One of the less emphasized techniques in conducting educational researches is the use of meta-analysis technique. As such, meta-analysis is a set of techniques used to combine the number of results of different studies to formulate a single more precise estimate of an effect. In a more scholarly definition, meta-analysis is a subset of systematic reviews and method to systematically combine pertinent qualitative and quantitative study data from several selected studies so as to develop a single conclusion. In other words, meta-analysis is a scientific examination on the results of several studies and a systematic formulation of results based on the significant findings of the examined studies. Apparently, meta-analysis is used to create a single conclusion out of several studies relevant to the context of the present study made. Logical connections through scientific findings of different studies are the fundamentals of meta-analysis.

Further, a meta-analysis is performed using studies gathered from searches in PsychoInfo, PubMed, ISI Web of Science and Google Scholar among others. There are 187 studies that provided original data on prevalence rates as the context of a study (Sagoe et al., 2014). Meta-analysis is a growing approach to evidence synthesis and network meta-analysis in particular represents a significant and developing method within education, health technology assessment and social sciences (Hall et al., 2015). Display of evidences on the research divergence and persistent gaps are obtained through the use of meta-analysis. Peer-reviewed studies using highly systematized implementation or use meta-analysis enabled researchers to compare findings within non-refereed work (Acar et al., 2017). The use of meta-analysis and institutional logics in higher education research profound a highly impactful scientific analysis (Tir & Karreth, 2018). Meta-analysis is best used when there are larger datasets illustrated from systematic reviews hence, meta-analysis provide informed estimates for a scientific outcome (Mikolajewicz & Komarova, 2019). Previous studies cited by researchers show that meta-analysis technique significantly advanced researchers logical examinations on the significant findings of several studies where data and results are compared to single out a scientific conclusion relative to the subject of the present studies conducted. Hence, the researchers find strong research gap specifically knowledge gap whereas previous studies only focused on the practical use and methods by which meta-analysis was employed.

On one hand, the researchers observed that most teachers and scholars in the field of education put less emphasis on the use of meta-analysis where they only practically relied on common research methods and usual statistical techniques. In addition, based on the collective observations of the researchers, most teachers in the basic education institutions used meta-analysis as not as frequent to common research methods including descriptive researches and phenomenological researches. In view of these foregoing conditions, the researchers advanced this study to assess the level of understanding on the significant implications of meta-analysis in the conduct of educational researchers.

OBJECTIVES

This study assessed the level of understanding of public elementary school teachers on the significant implications of meta-analysis in the conduct of educational researchers. The study specifically answered the following:

1. How may teachers' level of understanding on the implications of meta-analysis in the conduct of educational researches be assessed in terms of evidence-based practice, identification of research gaps and theory development?
2. How may teachers' level of understanding in using, defining and organizing meta-analysis studies be assessed in terms of applicability and variability concepts?
3. What are the challenges encountered by teachers in using meta-analysis in conducting educational researches?
4. Based from the findings, what program intervention may be proposed in order to develop or sustain teachers' level of understanding is using meta-analysis technique in conducting educational researches?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a sequential explanatory mixed method. Subject-respondents of the study were the 200 randomly selected public elementary school teachers in the Philippines who had already experienced and developed a meta-analysis studies relating to education. The researchers used simple random sampling in selecting the respondents. Apparently, the researchers used a researcher-made survey-questionnaire as the main research instrument of the study while they also developed guide questions which were used for Focus-Group Discussion (FGD). Thus, the developed survey-questionnaire contained two (2) significant parts. For part 1, it contained items relating to the teachers' level of understanding on the implications of meta-analysis while part 2 contained items relating to the teachers' level of understanding in using, defining and organizing meta-analysis studies. The researchers used a 4-Likert Scale such as 4-High Level of Understanding, 3-Moderate Level of Understanding, 2-Low Level of Understanding and 1-Extremely Low Level of Understanding. Apparently, the developed survey-questionnaire was used in order to measure the quantitative aspect of the study while the developed guide questions were employed in order to gather respondents' qualitative responses. Meanwhile, the developed survey-questionnaire was validated as the researchers sought the expertise of professionals specially those who were handling Research Methods subject in Graduate level. The same was subjected to internal consistency measure through pilot testing. Items under part 1 of the developed survey-questionnaire obtained a Cronbach Alpha result ($\alpha=.812$) while items under part 2 gained a Cronbach Alpha result ($\alpha=.715$) which were both verbally described as "Acceptable." On one hand, the developed guide questions were rated as "Highly Relevant" by the experts which meant that the questions were logical and coherent to the qualitative objective of the study. Further, in line with the actual data gathering phase, the researchers sent a formal communication letters to the respondents as the study was independently conducted. Also, they sent an informed consent through respondents' individual email addresses and stored the same for appropriate documentation. Thereafter, the researchers sent a Google Form link to the respondents through their personal email addresses which were gathered by communicating with them through their personal social media accounts. Once all quantitative data were gathered and organized, the researchers proceeded to the conduct of Focus Group Discussion where the researchers applied *commonality principle in qualitative research* which meant that when responses were similarly expressed and similar substances arising from their actual responses have reached, they suspended such data gathering for qualitative data. On one hand, relevant statistical tools were employed to quantify the quantitative data of the study such as the use of frequency, mean and general weighted mean. As to the qualitative data, the researchers employed thematic analysis through coding and decoding schemes. Hence, highest ethical standards in the conduct of a research study were strictly observed by the researchers. They stored the data gathered and deleted the same when this paper was completed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Advancing educational research through the use of meta-analysis technique is one of the most difficult yet comprehensive studies which teachers could be taken into consideration. Teachers' level of understanding on the implications of meta-analysis technique was significant to assess as it could reveal the current level of understanding of teachers in using meta-analysis to create highly comprehensive educational researches. In this line, the study carefully assess their level of understanding on the fundamental areas in educational researches by which meta-analysis could be best scientifically applied. Findings of the study would also enhance teachers' perceptions and scholarly appreciation on the credence of meta-analysis in administering educational researches. On one hand, this study could also be practically useful as it could serve as baseline for the development of localized research policies and programs in developing educational researches.

- 1. Teachers' Level of Understanding on the Implications of Meta-analysis in Educational Researches.** The results showed that teachers' level of understanding on the implications of meta-analysis technique in terms of evidence-based practice ($wm=2.32$) was low. This signified that teachers had a low level of understanding in aggregating scientific evidences from different studies to formulate scientific conclusions based on the context and nature of their educational studies conducted. In addition, the findings also implied that teachers had low level of understanding in making informed decisions based on the critical examinations and scientific interpretations of findings based on the comprehensive data presented in the different studies they have considered surrounding pedagogy and educational management studies. On the other hand, teachers' level of understanding on the implications of meta-analysis technique in terms of theory development ($wm=2.36$) was low. This

implied that teachers had low level of understanding in testing related and significant theories aligned with the nature and context of their studies conducted. This further indicated that teachers had low level of understanding in validating the theories they have through connecting them to the different studies they have gathered. In addition, this also implied that teachers obtained low level of understanding in interpreting theoretical constructs across the studies they have examined. Lastly, the results also showed that teachers possessed low level of understanding on the implications of meta-analysis technique in terms of identification of research gaps ($wm=2.45$). The findings showed that teachers possessed low level of understanding in identifying research gaps to the studies they have examined was low. Results of the study supported the findings of Macaskill et al. (2016) which revealed that test of meta-analysis of test accuracy provides summaries of the results of the relevant studies where researchers found it difficult to administer. Similar study also concluded that uncertainty of examination and estimates of the variability between studies around estimates posed greater confusion specially on newbie researchers. Practically, the study implicated that schools through school heads and other high ranking officials in the department should spearhead the use of meta-analysis among educational research through consistent and relevant workshops emphasizing the discussion and development of educational researches using meta-analysis techniques. To this effect, comprehensive and highly impactful educational researches could be obtained as the studies to be developed are in line with the comprehensive data across educational studies.

2. **Teachers' Level of Understanding in Using, Defining and Organizing Meta-Analysis.** The results showed that teachers' level of understanding using, defining and organizing meta-analysis in terms of applicability ($wm=1.83$) was low. This signified that teachers struggle to grasp how to apply meta-analysis in educational context. In addition, the results showed that teachers had low level of understanding in practically examining the relevance and impact of the examined studies as they were connected to the educational studies they administered specially in areas of teaching practices and educational management. In other words, teachers had low level of applying the significant data and findings presented on educational studies which they gathered while developing their education-related studies. On one hand, teachers' level of understanding in terms of using, defining and organizing meta-analysis in terms of variability ($wm=1.92$) was low. This signified that they had low level of understanding in recognizing different studies' structures yielding different results and importance specifically in interpretation. Results of the study supported the study of Lee (2017) which revealed that although there was a major advantage on the use of meta-analysis studies as it provided precise estimate of effect, the methods, means, understanding, application and interpretation caused researchers doing meta-analysis studies confused and misdirected. In addition, similar study emphasized that applying the structures and systematic process surrounding meta-analysis studies could provide less bias estimates. The study implicated that institution of research engagement among teachers and school heads highlighting the use of meta-analysis was essential. Hence, there should be policies that provide research incentives for teachers who would utilize meta-analysis studies among public basic institutions in the Philippines through laying clear, definite and precise policies.
3. **Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Using Meta-Analysis in Conducting Educational Researches.** Teachers expressed that they found meta-analysis as a very-challenging research in education-related topics because they lack on advanced statistical knowledge that would help them interpret and examine various findings and interpretations of several studies which were in line with the studies they administered. Further, they shared that complexity of meta-analysis hindered their comprehensive completion of educational researches they conducted as they were aware on the basic definition and principle of meta-analysis. According to them, such complexity enabled them to feel too much worried on the higher demands of studies relating to the context and scope of the current studies they administered. With their lack of knowledge in advanced statistics, this caused their discouragement as they possess lack of confidence. Feeling of intimidation commonly struck teachers when they used meta-analysis because for them, to engage with meta-analytic methods, it meant an outright prevention to complete hence, furnish their papers. The result of the study supported the study of Allen (2019) which concluded that meta-analysis was best way to reduce errors and bias in researches but it yielded complex processes and procedures. Similar study also showed that researchers

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management (IJETRM)

<https://ijetrm.com/>

with moderate level of knowledge in advanced statistics could experience that development of meta-analysis studies was complicated. As expressed by one of the participants:

“I do not really usually use meta-analysis because I know there are statistical models which are honestly, foreign to me.”

In addition, another participant made mentioned that:

“When we used meta-analysis model in our paper as part of subject requirement in my PhD degree, we consumed eternity really just to single out a founded conclusion from diverse range and complex studies on online journals.”

Also, another participant substantiated the statement of a participant:

“Ow! I really hate meta-analysis studies but they instituted good estimates specially extracting statistical calculations. But, I do not really have deeper knowledge on advanced statistics.”

- 4. Program Intervention.** This study proposed a development and implementation of program intervention of localized research writing workshops and training with a specific focus on meta-analysis techniques. The program aims to: (1) enhance the quality of educational researches conducted among public basic education institutions, (2) address the prevailing challenges which teachers experienced in developing educational researches, (3) promote evidenced-based and wide reach research studies through meta-analysis technique and (4) build capacity for teachers in using meta-analysis techniques to enable them to contribute to the broader educational research community.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The researchers expressed their sincerest gratitude to their professor, **Dr. Oliver E. Ortiz** for providing them an opportunity to develop this study. Also, the researchers emphasized the compassion, wisdom, support and encouragement of Dr. Ortiz Jr to further advance their competence through loving the culture of research. Also, the researchers expressed their gratitude to the Graduate School Department and the whole administration of Greenville College for expanding their reach through continued professional development. Also, the researchers were deeply indebted to their families and friends as they served as their source of strength, compassion and hope. Above all, the researchers praise an overflowing glory and grace of God in the Highest who is the true source of wisdom beyond the known and unknown universes.

CONCLUSION

Teachers had low level of understanding on the implications of meta-analysis in conducting educational researches as they had low level of understanding in terms of evidenced-based practice, theory development and identification of research gaps. They had also possessed a low level of understanding in using, defining and organizing meta-analysis studies specifically in terms of applicability and variability. Hence, teachers found it challenging to develop educational researches where meta-analysis was employed because of their lack of knowledge in advanced statistics. Hence, a program intervention through the implementation of localized research writing workshop and training should be administered. Thus, the program should emphasize and focus on the use and application of meta-analysis technique in educational researches as the same was not commonly employed in developing researches among public basic education institutions.

REFERENCES

- [1] Acar, S., Söderholm, P., & Brännlund, R. (2017). Convergence of per capita carbon dioxide emissions: Implications and meta-analysis. *Climate Policy*, 18(4), 512–525. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2017.1314244>
- [2] Allen, M. (2019). Understanding the practice, application, and limitations of meta-analysis. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 64(1), 74–96. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764219859619>
- [3] Hall, N. J., Kapadia, M. Z., Eaton, S., Chan, W. W., Nickel, C., Pierro, A., & Offringa, M. (2015). Outcome reporting in randomised controlled trials and meta-analyses of appendicitis treatments in children: A systematic review. *Trials*, 16(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-015-0783-1>

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management (IJETRM)

<https://ijetrm.com/>

- [4] Lee, Y. H. (2018). An overview of meta-analysis for clinicians. *The Korean Journal of Internal Medicine*, 33(2), 277–283. <https://doi.org/10.3904/kjim.2016.195>
- [5] Macaskill, P., Deeks, J., & Yemisi Yemisi Takwoingi. (2023). *Understanding the basics of meta-analysis and how to read a forest plot: As simple as it gets*. *The Journal of clinical psychiatry*. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33027562/>
- [6] Mikolajewicz, N., & Komarova, S. V. (2019). Meta-analytic methodology for basic research: A practical guide. *Frontiers in Physiology*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2019.00203>
- [7] Sagoe, D. (2014). *Methods Used in a Meta-Analysis and Meta-Regression Analysis of the Global Epidemiology of Anabolic-Androgenic Steroid Use*. <https://doi.org/10.4135/978144627305014537438>
- [8] Tir, J., & Karreth, J. (2018). The logic of institutional influence: Conceptual and methodological implications. *Oxford Scholarship Online*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780190699512.003.0005>